

Leadership Theories and Comparison of Them

Dr, Hidayet Tiftik¹, Şükrü Kılıç², Mehmet Sağlam³

¹Assit.Prof. ,Turgut Özal University, Ayvalı Mahallesi, Gazze Cad. No. 7 Keçiören , Ankara ,Turkey

²Turgut Özal University, Ayvalı Mahallesi, Gazze Cad. No. 7 Keçiören , Ankara ,Turkey

³Turgut Özal University, Ayvalı Mahallesi, Gazze Cad. No. 7 Keçiören , Ankara ,Turkey

Abstract

The objective of this term project was to distinguish leaders and managers and to compare the concepts of classical leadership and modern leadership.

Styles of leadership that are vital for current businesses were investigated; differences in classical and modern management styles were presented, responsibilities of a leader for the concept of modern leadership were identified; and differences between a manager and a leader were introduced.

Keywords: Leader; Manager; Classical Leadership; Modern Leadership; Differences between a Leader and a Manager.

Introduction

Leadership is one of areas about which we have very little information although institutions and experts on many various fields have performed excessive studies on it after 1900s together with changing world order. Yet a consensus could not be reached on what characteristics discriminate or could discriminate an effective leadership from an ineffective leadership. Descriptions related to the leadership may vary according to the condition and environment. Rather than defining leadership concept as a whole, it may include characteristics and behaviors observed in a specific environment conditions and in a specific time period (Karip, 1998).

At the present time leadership has become much more complicated than leader and follower relationship in classical meaning in the environment where the competition has become inevitable, moral and satisfaction feelings of employees have directly reflected on productivity and activity of organizations, benefiting from experiences, practices and abilities which people have has become most important potential (Ünal 2012).

Leaders of the 21st century face with much more different and complicated demands than past. Leaders had the power of changing their groups, organizations, personal values as they wish until 21st century, however today individuals to undertake key roles for organizations and organizations to emerge as economic and social wealth led to change of description and tasks of leadership.

Leadership behavior is completely related with behavior, attitude, state and status in relationships of the leader with people following him or group which the leader is responsible of management. Employees to act as a part of the institution or organization in it and perform their obligations in direction of the objectives and purposes of the organization they are in is to a large extent related with leadership styles which managers present. Therefore, this matter has been reviewed by many scientists and many classifications which are different from each other have been made in

Corresponding Author-- Hidayet Tiftik

the literature according to styles which leaders present. For many years, leadership styles have been separated in two sections generally and they have been defined as leadership styles focusing on work and person. The leadership which is old as much as the history of mankind has changed even as it has developed in accordance with conditions changing in time. Following these changes and improvements, future, innovation, change and reform concepts which have not been paid attention to or brought out previously in relation to leadership have been included in the leadership process. Leadership styles which feature future, innovation and change as a style have been referred to as transformational leadership. Leadership styles which are in the transformational leadership group have been named as change-driven leadership behaviors in scientific researches.

In work-oriented leadership which is among change-driven leadership styles, the focus and priority of the leader has become daily organizational performance. In work-oriented leadership style, managers use their authorities they get from their positions. Their employees are awarded in accordance with their efforts. Noticeable amendments are not performed very much in mission, vision, institutional structure and human resources operation of the organization. In people-oriented leadership however, vision defining, direction finding, working as a team, establishing talented teams, authorization and responsibility transferring is important. People-oriented leadership causes occurrence of a positive point of view by employees in terms of the institution. In change-driven leadership however, the leader gives opportunities to followers to develop their view for the future and increase their potentials and empower his followers. He takes care of his followers one by one. In conditions which require taking of risk, in situations which require authorization or responsibility, he encourages his followers. He supports creativity and self-confidence of followers. He ensures his followers to present more performance than expected or over their capacities by changing or improving their feeling and thought, belief and values. Briefly, in change-driven leadership, the leader enables his followers to be a leader in their own fields rather than being a machine. (Taş and Önder, 2010).

1. Description of Leadership Concept and its Relationship with Some Concepts

1.1. Description of Leadership

Since leader and leadership concepts are old as much as the history of mankind, in descriptions made for these concepts, it may vary according to the social, cultural and economic characteristics of the period in which the description has been made. Characteristics of the period being lived in caused the making of separate leader or leadership description for each period.

It is required not to perceive leadership solely as a concept related with an organization structure. It is a process emerged by a certain human society to follow a certain person around certain purposes. Nevertheless this process may emerge in formal institutions and organizations, it also emerges in informal institutions and organizations (Ertürk, 2001).

Making a clear and comprehensive description of leadership has difficulties. It is required to seek for reasons of these in smooth and deceptive characteristics of the leadership fact. Indeed, leadership is a function related with the relationship established between the leader and his followers and quality of the mutual interaction between the leader and followers rather than a title or hierarchical position. Leadership is not related with having authority or power on followers but influencing and directing followers (Gürsel 2014).

If we would like to make some description on leader and leadership; leadership is a person to stand out in the process of controlling social activities. Another description is convincing people to manage them in direction of determined aims. Another definition is sum of information and ability of being able to gather a group of people around certain purposes and prod them into action for performing these purposes. And another definition is ability of the leader to transmit his intimacy to his followers, to assign different meanings to behaviors in different situations, to prod his followers into action in direction of purposes. However, leader is; the person who organizes activities of members of the organization in line with organization purposes by directing them (Demir et al. 2010).

If we define the leader with essential functions and characteristics, leader is; the person who has efficiency and ability of keeping some certain group of people who live in company together for certain targets and purposes, directing people, putting them into effect, who can direct followers about where they can reach from which way, who has objectives and who can determine vision and mission and who has characteristics such as creativeness, foresight, understanding, fidelity, honesty, stability, tendency of teamwork, communication skill, problem resolving and intuitional thinking skill, charisma and inspiration (Erkutlu, 2014).

When we combine all leadership characteristics mentioned above, mutual characteristics and essential concepts emerging have come together under four essential factors as target, leader, followers and togetherness.

- i) Target; The concept which enables individuals to live together and which consists of needs, purposes, mutual wishes.
- ii) Leader; The member of the organization who can influence followers or people living together.
- iii) Followers; Group members who accept the affect constituted by the leader in the group and who follows the leader.

- iv) Togetherness; The main element consisting of factors such as competency of the group, level of relationships within group, availability of mutual purposes and level of incentive etc. (Erkutlu, 2014).

As it can be understood from made definitions, leadership is a concept which entirely occurs by means of human, influence and purpose factors. As is understood, in leadership concept; human, influence and target factors have occurred in together and we can say that there is a structure which mutually and continuously affect each other.

Table 1: Leader and Leadership Descriptions

Author	Description
Hemphill and Coons (1957)	Leadership is the behavior of management of group activities by the individual in line with shared purpose.
Bass (1960)	Leadership is sum of information and ability of being able to gather a group of people around certain purposes and prod them into action for performing these purposes
Stogdill (1974)	Leadership is being able to prod a structure into action with mutual behavior and consensus and being able to continue this action.
Katz and Kahn (1978)	Leadership is interaction which have been developed except routine works and much more above them in direction of mechanical structure of the organization
Burus (1978)	Leadership emerges when motivations of followers increased, met and satisfied by using corporate, political, psychological and other resources.
Bennis and Nanus (1985)	Leadership is the driving power behind organizations in rapidly changing world for them to keep step with this change.
Yukl (1989)	Leadership is a person to convince other individuals when he acts as he said by emphasizing that progress will be made
Bass (1990)	Leader is the individual who becomes different from others due to the influence he made on determination of the purpose and required activities to reach the purpose.
Robbins (1996)	Leadership is the capability of influencing the group in direction of reaching purposes.
Ankan (2001)	Leader is the person who has been assigned for directing group activities related to certain targets in the group and ensuring coordination or who undertakes these functions in the absence of an assigned leader.
Zel (2001)	Leadership is the sum of information and skills of gathering a group of people together and of prodding them into action, influencing them for performance of these purposes.
Yukl (2012)	Leadership is the process of influencing employees for understanding needs and making consensus on them and putting into action effectively and at the same time it includes the whole of individual and collective efforts in reaching shared purposes.
Tabak and et al. (2007)	Leadership is, if there isn't any, to create a group or team in line with a certain purpose and target and if there is, prod it into action, manage and make it successful by making it have team spirit.

Reference: Erkutlu 2014

As it can be understood from above table, many authors have made many definitions in leadership area and these definitions vary in accordance with conditions of the period they are in. Even the same author have made different definitions for leadership in different periods.

As a result, for an organization which is in the purpose of an effective management and development, one of important concepts as well as leadership and change is teamwork. Teamwork has an important position and benefit in enhancement of present potential of the organization. By means of teamwork, organizations are able to find more rationalist solutions and way outs for existing problems. Information sharing and communication in organizations will operate in a more healthy way by means of teamwork (Çetin, 2008).

1.2. Discrimination between Manager and Leader

Descriptions which are different from each other are made between management and leadership. A definition defines management as performing a work, fulfilling and undertaking the responsibility and conducting the responsibility. However, leadership is influencing, directing, guiding in line with purposes, effectively being involved in an activity and effective appearance. According to this, in an organizational structure, managers give importance on rules, procedures, inspection, acting in line with certain conditions and operation of rules. Leaders however, is related with active communication, creation of innovative ideas and putting new ideas into practice. Based on this description, manager is called as the person who continues in other word maintains the occurrence and leader is called as the person who performs innovation or who achieves to perform change, who puts into practice innovation or change together with his followers.

In a general meaning, management is ensuring all opportunities of an organization are brought together with the purpose of service or product manufacturing which is main purpose of a commercial institution or organization. Manager uses his authority he obtained from his position to be able to fulfill these functions. In other words, while management is an authorization and obligation obtained by means of having an authorization, leadership is ability of using the power by an individual which comprise of characteristics or abilities which are specific to that individual. In the stage of directing or influencing followers, while managers use the power or authority they have obtained in accordance with their positions, leaders obtain their power from their characters or abilities which are specific to themselves and from the support given by their followers. (Demir et al. 2010).

While leaders discover inconsistent, changeable, unclear situations which we encounter, managers submit before these situations. And there are very important differences between these two (Ünal. 2012).

Leadership is not only seen in hierarchical structures but also in informal structures and relationships. The most determinant characteristic of leadership is being able to create a team of followers which is able to obtain effective results and ability of making the effectiveness of these followers continuous. The basic ability which a leader must have is the success of results which the leader ensured together with his followers who have acknowledged the leader and trusted him and believed him and continuation of these successful results. Managers however, get the power from the hierarchy. People who have personal control area on others are managers. The discrimination between manager and leader can be explained by means of the table below. (Erkutlu, 2014).

Table 2: Basic Differences Between Leader and Manager	
Manager	Leader
Administrator	Innovative
Repeater	Original
Ensures continuation	Ensures development
Focuses on the system and structures	Focuses on people
Trusts the inspection	Trusts the rightness
Has short-term vision	Has long-term vision
Asks questions in the form of how and when	Why and what for questions are important
Always skims through the floor	Skims through the horizontal plane.
Is a good soldier in classical meaning	Is himself.
His thoughts are correct	Is in correct thinking.
Accepts the current situation	Challenges the current situation.
Reference: (Bennis, 1989), Akt. Erkutlu 2014 p 5	

In summary, leadership is not a management method which is superior than the management or which can be applied in replacement of management. Leadership and management are two different action form which completes each other. A leader should also have management characteristics which a manager has.

Before starting classical and modern leadership theories, it is beneficial to compare both approach by means of the table.

Table 3: Classical And Modern Leadership Understanding

Leadership Factors	Classical Leadership Understanding	Modern Leadership Understanding
IDEAS	Directing is related with daily problems rather than comprehensive work matters. Development programmes are daily and limited with what is taught at schools	Directing depends on personal opinions of the leader, forces people to develop their own point of views. Development programmes depend on real events in daily living.
VALUES	Moreover leaders explain organizational values for populations in the form of superficial messages.	Leaders help people combine their own values with values of business place and resolve emerging paradox when values conflict with each other.
ENERGY	Programmes cannot go beyond throwing a bone. When people are back to work they have already forgotten the taste of the honey	Programmes are continuous, leaders determine frames to be based on for motivation.
HORIZON	Professional educators give importance not to making difficult decisions but to timing and determination of priority	Leaders personally be helpful about what to be done to people who cannot fulfill expected performance or value standards.
LEADERSHIP FOCUS	Leadership gives importance to compilation of technical competencies in the field of strategy, financing etc.	Leadership gives weight to samples in the base of personal narratives.
ROLE OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT	Senior managers content their selves with supporting development programmes, they participate into these programmes from time to time only to be a participant.	Senior managers take part as an active participant, they lead to the whole or a part of programmes for development of leadership characteristics.

Reference: Çetin 2008

2. Modern Leadership Theories

In today's time where values and way of performance of a work rapidly change, expectations of people from leaders and management methods rapidly change as everything. Change caused world order and following expectations, new leadership and leader models confront of us.

New leaders are individuals who are innovative and take part in the target population as follower or being followed, who determine consumption and decision making behaviors, who make their decision in a quite intensive and excessive consumption environment which rapidly changes and in which communication and interaction is pretty easy.

If we need to list consumption tools which affect individuals and their decisions, they can be listed as follows; Global communication tools, shopping malls where people intensively visit (relationship between people and good-humored sales officer and customer is being re-established, fast food restaurants (eat fast, consume fast and you have time for fun), national chain stores, theatre, music (it keeps naughty children busy who have objection to the system), internet, credit cards (it creates feeling of unlimited spending), discount stores (feeling of reaching the luxury and the quality), sport centers (opportunity for the individual to change his body), sites with luxury entrances, education environments (there are equipment which make the education funny) and even hospitals...

New leadership styles show the wanted characteristics of classical leadership styles by individuals. For classical leaders, reassurance, being honesty, diligence, intimacy concepts were important in influencing followers and they were also sufficient. Same characteristics are also requested from new leaders however in fact, the distance between being so in real and creating as if so perception has lessened. (Yıldız, 2012).

Table 6: Developments which have been Revealed in Organizations by Improvements

Previous Situation	Current Situation
From Big and Various Manufacturing Headquarters	To Small Manufacturing Units
From Vertical Integration	To Working with Sub-Contractor
Greatness Economy	Flexibility
High and Incisive Organizations	Flat and Plain Organizations
Bureaucratic Personality	Entrepreneurship
Increasing Market Share	New Markets
Collective Marketing	Niche Marketing
Quantitative	Quality

Reference; Ünal 2012

Changing world order has caused some changes in today's companies as is in all areas. In the table, impacts of experienced changes can be seen from way of work performance of today's companies to organizations, to manufacture or service.

2.1. Charismatic Leadership

Charismatic leadership subject has been investigated by different departments of the science. Among these departments, there are various departments of social sciences such as sociology, psychology, organizational behavior, history, management, human resources and political sciences.

Charismatic leaders stop needs, values, resources and aspirations of group members being individual and they make them become mutual needs of the group. For that reason, people who follow the leader stay connected to missions of charismatic leaders. In charismatic leadership, followers trust the leader, they give huge importance on values and their motivations increase. Charismatic leader leads his followers and inspires them. Charismatic leaders are individuals who give confidence to their followers, who arouse respect on them, who ensure their followers to look to future with positive ness, who facilitate their followers to see things what are really important in their lives, who arouse objective feeling in followers and who stimulate them (Gül and Aykanat, 2012).

General characteristic of charismatic leaders is they have powerful beliefs, they trust themselves and they have a great impact on their followers with this belief and confidence. They are imitated by their followers. They make their followers feel that they trust them and they express what they expect from their followers by means of the impact they create on their followers. They both ensure occurrence of group mission on followers and also individual motivation. Charismatic leaders generally appear in the society in crisis environments. They wholly dominate the crisis environment and make self-sacrifice when necessary and they use their individual charisma and they implement strategies which have not been previously implanted and which are unusual. (Erktulu, 2014).

We have expressed that charismatic leaders generally appear in distressed periods such as crisis and disorder. When we have a look at the history, the whole of great charismatic leaders such as Atatürk, Gandhi, Hitler and M. Luther King who made their mark in history and have been accepted evenhandedly by everybody have appeared in negative conditions of their countries.

The need of societies for a hero or rescuer in distressed periods such as economic crisis, wars, demographic factors or great depressions is much more than usual. This means that the required environment for charismatic leader to appear has occurred. A hero is always needed for societies which have not sufficiently developed or could not become organized to resolve many problems or to set things right again. (Gül and Aykanat, 2012).

Results of research and studies made on leadership have put emphasizes on charismatic leadership. In the philosophy of charismatic leadership theory, leader is able to influence populations thanks to his personal capabilities. Charismatic leaders to have potency motivation in a high ratio made them have motivation of being leader in a high ratio. Capabilities such as creating image, being an example for followers, giving confidence, ensuring motivation of followers are basic characteristics which a charismatic leader should have (Demir et al. 2010).

2.2. Transformational Leadership

If we describe transformational leadership as the last point which modern leadership theory has reached, this wouldn't be wrong. Basic philosophy of transformation leadership is integrating managerial philosophy which is required for renovation and transformation process of organizations and way of work performance. Transformational leaders create necessary conditions required by the organization together with the vision they have created for businesses to reach the points they have aimed for the future and convert transformations around for an advantage and opportunity for the company (Özalp and Öcal, 2000).

Transformational leadership is related with long-term targets and politics of the company in nature. In transformational leadership, followers are directed by giving them targets in line with a vision instead of numerical or material targets based on the communication between the leader and the followers on corporate level. In transformational leadership, with targets which can be performed in long-term, followers are aware that following uncovering capabilities and abilities of followers and increasing and improving self-confidence of followers, long-term targets can be fulfilled. (Erkuş and Günlü, 2008).

In transformational leadership, the leader performs motivation by making suggestion to employees, performs intellectual stimulation and creates energy on them which enable them to fulfill their objectives. Organization leader ensures increase of focus in line with objectives and purposes of employees in the institution by bringing out a vision and mission awareness in the institution. Employees prioritize aims and interests of the institution or group by pushing their own interests and aims into the background. Transformational leader realizes existing tendency, needs and desires of followers or individuals who have follower potential and uses this need to motivate the follower, makes the follower take into action by addressing requirements and desires of the follower. (Karip, 1998).

Basic task of transformational leader is to kick off transformation in the organization in parallel with changing environment conditions and to give confidence and courage to organization employees required for transformation and make them reach mission and objectives of the organization.

It has been suggested that transformational leadership has four essential factors (Erkutlu, 2014);

- **Charisma:** Showing confident, clear and understandable objective to followers, providing motivational support to them in relation with reaching this objective, giving optimism and showing at each possibility that he is with followers.
- **Intellectual Encouragement:** Encouraging followers about getting over the current situation, approaching problems from a new and different perspective, being innovative and creative□□
- **Place Individual Importance to Followers:** Frankly approaching feelings, wishes and opinions of followers, placing particular importance to their need of developing renewing themselves, behaving fair and equal to them one by one. Transformational leaders establish one by one relationship with followers, they give importance to personal development of followers and they develop empathy.
- **Giving Inspiration:** In transformational leadership, the leader is a role model for his juniors. He acts in a way to affect, motivate and inspire them. Main reason of the leader to be a source of inspiration for followers is making followers exceed their expected performance.

2.3. Servant Leadership

The essential philosophy of servant leadership is the leader to see himself at zero point and to perceive us concept before me concept. The leader devotes himself for wellness, happiness and future of members of the group he is in and for the group.

Together with the transformation and development came with globalization, a renovation and transformation process has started in structures, way of work performance of organizations and even in all levels of organizations till leadership and management understandings.

It is thought that an environment where human affairs and value given to the human are at the forefront will be passed from a robotic environment where sentimentality and human behaviors are not given importance, electronic designs outweigh. Trying to be something else without learning to be a human in this transformation process which will be experienced and under responsibility of this, managing works and persons by rejecting laws of the soul and universe just as rowing against the tide will not show result. Because of these reasons, despite identified as superior or manager, a manager who gives order his juniors he is working with and expects this order to be fulfilled, is not a superior or leader and they need to be leaders who complete each other with their followers, who add value personal development of followers and who serves his followers. As a natural consequence of this changing situation, servant leadership approach has emerged. Factors of servant leadership concept referred as Patterson's model can be explained as below (Bakan and Doğan, 2004).

- Having Ethical Love: We can define meaning of the word of “agapao” which means making right things with right reasons at the right time in ancient greek as an ethical love. In this ethical love, demands of each of group member are named as a follower or group member who has demands and objectives. The leader however is the person who has this love and primarily focuses on his employees and their basic requirements while showing his ethical love and later takes into account their abilities and finally focuses on the benefit of the organization.
- Being Modest: giving priority and importance to requirements and demands of other members of the group instead of leader’s or group members’ own requirements and demands. In servant leadership, the leader does not think himself superior or better than other group members and has latitude.
- Being self-sacrificing: In servant leadership, the leader tries to be helpful to other group members without expecting any return or expectation and he is willing about this help. He doesn’t have a purpose of an extra favor or return against aids he will be making to other group members.
- Having Vision: In servant leadership, the leader is the person who has long-term objectives and purposes, who creates a vision and future for the institution and who is able to give direction to followers in line with these vision and future.
- Confidence: In the base of servant leadership there is confidence concept. As a natural result of the leader to act equally and ethically, a feeling of confidence occurs in followers and group members against the leader.
- Empowering Employees: In servant leadership, the leader gives authorizations to employees about works they are doing by giving responsibility to employees about their works he is working together and thus the control over employees is released.
- Serving: In servant leadership, the base of serving concept means leaders to bring out interests and benefits of employees working in the institution rather than bringing out their own personal interests and benefits, and consequently acting at this direction.

Fig 1: Servant Leadership Expanding Circles Model (Reference; Erkutlu 2014)

2.4. Ethical Leadership

Although the philosophy and facts of ethical leadership are similar with servant leadership, its main goal is it is a leadership style used to place ethics or ethical operation logic in institutions and organizations. The main goal in ethical leadership is in managerial decisions and operation processes, making existing ethical dimensions clear and putting them forward. Creating ethical principles which direct making and giving decision processes in organizations and defending them. Ethical leadership concept is not a concept to which organizations are quite strange or which they have newly heard. Many employees of institutions or organizations have essential moral dimensions related with the business in their area of task and responsibility. In many decisions given by leaders there is an ethical basis or ethical criterion. Besides, all kind of leaderships also include values and being manipulated or motivated by a certain philosophic point of view (Uğurluoğlu and Çelik, 2009).

If we approach ethical leadership in terms of employees or organizations, it can be expressed as the most ideal leadership style in terms of applicability of the democracy. In researches made to identify and tell ethical leadership, ten essential characteristics have emerged which will explain ethical leadership and will ensure its operability in an organization (Erkutlu, 2014).

- Ethical leaders regularly mention about mutual values, ethical standards and ensure these are understood, perceived and implemented.
- Ethical leaders give responsibility to people. Such leaders keep themselves and other people responsible about behaving in compliance with ethical values.
- Ethical leaders become example for other employees in the organization with their behaviors and expect other employees also act according to ethical principles.
- Ethical leaders do not rule out their followers and guidance principles in stages of decision making process. They protect ethical values at each behavior they make.
- Ethical leaders take care of politics and its applications to be in compliance.
- Ethical leaders constitute time and source for the purpose of helping people to get required confidence and ability in terms of transforming correct beliefs to good behaviors.
- Ethical leaders pay attention to feelings, opinions and reactions of all other people in their influence area.
- Since complying with ethical rules and values is a result of a richness, ethical leaders perform a number of small improvements in many areas.
- Ethical leaders use their missions, visions and values as a measure when deciding about hiring personnel to the institution they are connected to and making promotion.
- Ethical leaders come to the forefront and motivate in terms of being pathfinder for ethics instead of blaming someone else or waiting for others.

2.5. Strategic Leadership

The change which is being experienced in today's economy has also spread management styles of companies and companies which have been managed by families or bosses have been replaced by companies which have multiple shareholders and which do not have one owner. Nowadays, companies have transformed to global companies which are acting in many countries and which have tens of even hundreds of shareholders. This transformation experienced in activity areas and structures of companies has brought out Strategic leadership theory which is a new leadership concept. The need of senior manager in companies has increased and CEO (Chief Executive Officer) concept has emerged. Today's companies CEOs have accepted alone strategic leadership responsibilities. As being strategic leaders of organizations, essential task of CEOs are to choose vision for their organizations and to create required environment and conditions to reach this vision.

When the task and responsibility falling to strategic leaders resulted in financial achievements, strategic leaders have been seen as a hero or rescuer for companies. However, together with the globalization brought by 21st century, uncertainty environment for organizations and different economics and social changes in different markets have caused them to face up with unpredictable environment conditions. While change in industries was being performed linear in past centuries, important competitors were also not global but usually local. The new competitive structure of global economy has blocked determination of the direction of the organization with point of view of one individual and has differentiated structure of organizations of 21st century and strategic leadership implementations. Table 1 indicates important differences between effective strategic leadership implementations of 20th and 21st century (Uğurluoğlu and Çelik, 2009).

Table 8: Strategic Leadership Implementations

20 th Century Implementations	21 st Century Implementations
Output driven	Output and process driven
Patient and Confident	Confident but not arrogant
Tries to get the information	Tries to get the information and use it to get result
Directs creativeness of people	Releases creativeness of people and feeds
Work flows are determined according to hierarchy	Work flows are effected from relationships
The importance of integrity is mentioned explicitly	The importance of integrity is indicated by actions
Respect is requested	Respect is wanted to be gained
Differences are tolerated	Differences are looked for
Reacts to environmental change	Acts to sense environmental change in advance
Works as a great leader	Works as a leaders and member of a great group
Employees are seen as a resource	Organizational employees are seen as a critical resource
Essentially being worked with a local attitude of mind	Essentially being worked with a global attitude of mind
Investment is made for development of employees	Investment is made on an important amount for continuous development of employees

Reference: Ireland R.D. and Hitt, M.A. (2005) akt. Uğurluoğlu and Çelik

3. Conclusion

Since the existence of mankind, leadership concept or leader has always been together with people both in within groups and company and organizational structures and crisis and depression periods and in time, changing environment, economic and demographic or social factors caused changes in description of leadership and way of requirements.

Before industrial revolution, in classical meaning, leader is perceived as a superior who was perceived as manager, who got his power from rules and hierarchical structure and whose task is make people or groups perform standard works in the frame of certain rules and templates. In 20th century, however, leader concept has been discriminated from manager concept and the power and authorization which the manager gets from hierarchy or rules has been obtained by leader from his own natural abilities, behaviors, his decisions in the organizations in other words the leader has provided the source of the power from his own individual capabilities.

The sole reason which make leader emerge was not global world order, economic factors or organizational changes and transformations occurred in the society has brought to light the need of societies for leader in also crisis and depression periods.

Changing world order has needed different leadership models in different periods and different leadership models have emerged in line with requirements occurring at each period. For this reason, it is quite difficult to talk about a single leadership model and make a single leadership description which is applicable for each period and society. Nowadays, characteristics expected from applicable leadership can be defined as person who makes out individual abilities of followers, empowers followers and separates individual abilities and ensures performance of long-term objectives of company and institutions with distinctive characteristics of individuals.

4. References

- [1] Bakan, İ. and Doğan, İ. F., (2012), “Hizmetkâr Liderlik”, *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2(2), 1-12.
- [2] Çetin, C., (2008), “Yöneticilerin Liderlik Stilleri, Değişim Yönetimi ve Ekip Çalışması Arasındaki İlişkilerin Çok Yönlü Olarak Değerlendirilmesi”, *İstanbul Ticaret Odası Yayınları*, İstanbul.
- [3] Demir, C. et al., (2010), “Liderlik Yaklaşımları ve Liderlik Tarzlarına İlişkin Araştırma”, *Alanya İşletme Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2(1), 129-152.
- [4] Erkuş, A. and GÜNLÜ, E., (2008) , “Duygusal Zekânın Dönüşümcü Liderlik Üzerine Etkileri”, *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İşletme Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9(2), 187-209.
- [5] Erkutlu, H.V., (2014), “Liderlik Kuramlar ve Yeni Bakış Açılıarı”, First ed., Elif Yayınevi, Ankara.
- [6] Ertürk, M., (2001), “İşletme Biliminin Temel İlkeleri”, Beta Basım Yayın Dağıtım, İstanbul.
- [7] Gül, H. and Aykanat, Z., (2012), “Karizmatik Liderlik ve Örgüt Kültürü İlişkisi Üzerine Araştırma”, *Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 16(1), 17-36.
- [8] Gündüz, Y. and ve Dedekorkut, S.E., (2014), “Yıkıcı Liderlik”, *Mersin Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 10(1), 95-104.
- [9] Gürsel, M., (2014), “Yönetime Çağdaş Yaklaşımlar”, First ed., Çizgi Kitapevi, Konya.
- [10] İbrahimoglu, N., (2011), “İşletmelerde Liderlik ve Kriz Yönetimi İlişkisi”, *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 10(2), 731-747.
- [11] Karip, E., (1998), “Dönüşümcü Liderlik”, *Gazi Üniversitesi Gazi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 4(16), 443-465.
- [12] Naktiyok, A., (2006), “E-Liderlik: E-Liderlik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesine Yönelik Bir Araştırma”, *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi İşletme Fakültesi Dergisi*, 7(1), 19-40.
- [13] Özalp, İ. and Öcal, H., (2000), “Örgütlerde Dönüştürücü (Transformational) Liderlik Yaklaşımı”, *Balıkesir Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 3(4), 207-226.
- [14] Taş, A. and Önder, E., (2010), “Yöneticilerin Liderlik Davranışlarının Personel İş Doyumuna Etkisi”, *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(32), 17-30.
- [15] Uğurluoğlu, Ö. and Çelik, Y., (2009), “Örgütlerde Stratejik Liderlik ve Özellikleri”, *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sağlık İdaresi Dergisi*, 12(2), 121-144.
- [16] Ünal, M., (2012), “Bilgi Çağında Değişim ve Liderlik”, *Marmara Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32(1), 297-310.
- [17] Nuran, Y., (2012), “Yeni Zamanlar ve Yeni Liderlik Anlayışı”, *Ankara Avrupa Çalışma Dergisi*, 11(1), 119-134.